

Lodhra Sheethadi Agada in Mandali Visha - A Review

Dr. Sreekutty P.V.¹, Dr. Shrinidhi R.², Dr. Shubha P.U.³, Dr. Chaithra Hebbar⁴

¹Post Graduate Scholar, Department of PG studies in Agadatantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Udupi-574118.Karnataka, India

²Associate Professor, Department of PG studies in Agadatantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Udupi-574118.Karnataka, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of PG studies in Agadatantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Udupi-574118.Karnataka, India

⁴Professor and Head, Department of PG studies in Agadatantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Udupi-574118.Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

There are many *Agada Yogas* widely practiced by *Visha vaidyas*. *Lodhra Sheethadi Agada* is one of the practically used formulation in the management of *Mandali Sarpa Visha*. This formulation is explained in *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika*, *Prayogasamuchayam*, *Lakshanamritham* etc. It consists of nine drugs in the reference given in *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika* whereas ten ingredients in that of *Prayogasamuchayam*. This formulation can be administered as *Paana* as well as *Lepa*. The administration of *Lodra Sheethadi Agada* in *Kasaya* form is clinically practiced in present era. This paper is an attempt to review the yoga '*Lodhra Sheethadi Agada*'.

KEYWORDS: *Mandali Sarpavisha, Agada, Lodhra Seethadi Agada.*

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
20 October 2022

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Keraleeya Visha Chikitsa granthas like *Prayogasamuchayam*¹, *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika*², *Kriya kaumudi* etc contains numerous preparations for the effective management of *Vishajanya rogas* including *Sarpa Visha*. *Mandali Sarpa Visha* is a *Pitta* predominant condition which shows clinical manifestations like *Sopha*, *Daha* etc. *Lodra Sheethadi Agada* has been mentioned in *Prayogasamuchayam*, *Visha vaidya jyotsnika* in the context of *Mandali visha*. This article is an attempt to review the ingredients, properties, mode of action and uses of *Lodhra Seethadi Agada*.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Name of *Yoga*: *Lodhra Sheethadi Agada*.
Lodhra Sheethadi Agada is mentioned in *Triteeya Paricheda* of *Prayogasamuchayam*¹, written by Kochunni Tamburan. It is also explained in *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika*² while explaining about the treatment for *Mandali Sarpa Visha Chikitsa*. Only nine ingredients have been mentioned by *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika* whereas in *Prayoga samuchayam Neeli* has been considered as the tenth ingredient. Reference from *Prayogasammuchayam* is clearly mentioning that this *Yoga* can be used in the form of *Paana* as well as *Lepa*. In *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika* it is advised to administer this formulation along with *Seetha Jala* or *Naaliker* (*tender coconut water*). This can be also administered in *Kwatha* form.

Table 1: Ingredients of *Lodhra Seethadi Kasaya* and Botanical name³.

<i>Lodhra</i> ³	<i>Symplocos racemosa</i>	<i>Symplocaceae</i>
<i>Chandana</i> ⁴	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn	<i>Santalaceae</i>
<i>Haridra</i> ⁵	<i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>
<i>Daruharidra</i> ⁶	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	<i>Berberidaceae</i>

Lodhra Sheethadi Agada in Mandali Visha - A Review

<i>Sarala</i> ⁷	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	<i>Pinaceae</i>
<i>Arka</i> ⁸	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>
<i>Bilwa</i> ⁹	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	<i>Rutaceae</i>
<i>Manjishta</i> ¹⁰	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	<i>Rubiaceae</i>
<i>Paatala</i> ¹¹	<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i>	<i>Bignonaceae</i>
<i>Neeli</i> ¹²	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i>	<i>Papilionaceae</i>

Table 2: Lodra Seethadi Agada Ingredients and properties

Sl no	Drug	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Vipaka	karma
1	<i>Lodhra</i> ³	<i>Kaṣāya</i>	<i>Rukṣa</i>	<i>Sita</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pithakapha Samaka, Sitagrahi, Cakṣuṣya, Sothahara, Jwarahara, Trṣṇāni grahana, Visaghna.</i>
2.	<i>Chandana</i> ⁴	<i>Tikta, Madhura</i>	<i>Rukṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Śīta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pittakapha samaka, Trṣṇāhara, Raktaprasadaka, Dahahara, , Twakdoṣa hara, Kuṣṭhaghna, Jwaraghna</i>
3.	<i>Haridra</i> ⁵	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Rukṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Uṣṇa</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphapitta samaka, Twacya, , Sothahara, Vranahara, Kandughna, Visaghna, Kusthaghna, Sitapittahara</i>
4.	<i>Daruharidra</i> ⁶	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Rukṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Uṣṇa</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pittakapha samaka,, Kandughna, Vṛṇahara, Viṣaghna, Kuṣṭhaghna, Raktasodhaka</i>
5.	<i>Sarala</i> ⁷	<i>Tikta, Kaṣāya</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Uṣṇa</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphavata shamaka, Kandughna, Vranahara</i>
6.	<i>Arka</i> ⁸	<i>Tikta, Madhura</i>	<i>Laghu, Rukṣa, Tikṣna</i>	<i>Uṣṇa</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphavata samaka, Kusthaghna, Kandughna, Viṣaghna, Vranaropaka, Sophahara.</i>
7.	<i>Bilwa</i> ⁹	<i>Kaṣāya, Tikta</i>	<i>Rukṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Uṣṇa</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphavata samaka, Sothahara, Chardighna</i>
8.	<i>Manjishta</i> ¹⁰	<i>Kaṣāya, Tikta</i>	<i>Guru, Rukṣa</i>	<i>Uṣṇa</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pittakapha samaka, Varnya, Raktaśodhaka, Viṣaghna, Sothahara, Kusthaghna, Vranahara, Jwaraghna.</i>
9.	<i>Paatala</i> ¹¹	<i>Tikta, Kasaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Rukṣa</i>	<i>Usna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Tridosha samaka, Dahahara, Raktapittahara, Sothahara, Trishnanigrahana, Chardighna.</i>
10	<i>Neeli</i> ¹²	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, Rukṣa</i>	<i>Usna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vatakapha Samaka, Visaghna, Jwarahara.</i>

Method of preparation

In *Prayogasamuchayam* it is mentioned that this formulation can be used in the form of *Paana* as well as *Lepa*. But in *Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika* the use of this formulation along with *Seetha jala* and *Naalikera* is explained. All the drugs should be taken in equal quantity and made into fine powdered and used in appropriate form with the mentioned *Anupanas*. Since dosage is not mentioned in any of the references, standard dose of *Kasaya* (2 Pala – app 96ml) can be given internally .

Diagram 1: Analysis of Rasa of ingredients of Lodhra Sheethadi Agada

Diagram 2: Analysis of Guna of ingredients of Lodhra Sheethadi Agada

Diagram 3: Analysis of Virya of ingredients of Lodhra Sheethadi Agada

Diagram 4: Analysis of Vipaka of ingredients of Lodhra Sheethadi Agada

DISCUSSION

Lodhra Sheethadi Agada is an effective formulation used for Mandali Sarpa Visha by Visha Vaidyas. Among the drugs 56% are having Tikta rasa and 31% is having Kasaya rasa which pacifies pitta dosha. 47% of the drugs are Ruksha guna and 42% are laghu guna which helps in spread of medicine fastly. All the drugs are Katu vipaka which pacifies kapha dosha. 90% of the drugs are Kaphapitta samaka and most of them are Vishagna, Vrana ropana, and with Kushtaghna properties. The medium used for administering this yoga are Sheeta jala and Naalikera jala which will pacifies Pitta dosha. Clinically this yoga can be given in Mandali Sarpa Visha which shows Pitta predominance and in other vishaja as well as Pittaja rogas.

CONCLUSION

Mandali sarpa visha is a condition of pitta predominance. Lodhra Sheethadi Kasaya is found to be very effective in the management of mandali sarpa visha as well as in other pittaja vyadhis. It is widely practised by Keraleeya Visha Vaidyas. There is a slight difference of opinion regarding the ingredient in the available references. Clinically practicing yoga has mentioned in this article. All the drugs are easily available and can be prepared and administered easily. Further studies has to be conducted to prove its clinical efficacy.

REFERENCES

- I. Kochunni thampuran, Prayoga Samuchaya, Thrissur, Kerala: Sulabha books; astama parichedanam, p68.
- II. C.M Sreekrishnan, Visha Vaidya Jyotsnika an English translation, Department of Agada Tantra Vaidyaratnam P.S Varrier Ayurveda College Kottakal, 3rd edition, pg no ; 45
- III. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 550
- IV. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 213
- V. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 333
- VI. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 345
- VII. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 3, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 680
- VIII. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 86
- IX. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 185

Lodhra Sheethadi Agada in Mandali Visha - A Review

- X. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 647
- XI. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 2, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 577
- XII. Hegde Prakash L, A Harini, A textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Volume 3, New Delhi: Chaukamba Publications,p 532